

Reading and Learning Errors: A Study on Young Learners of Indranagar Khasia Punjee of Cachar District

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Abstract

Reading is the process of expressing own opinion and thinking in a very systematic way; it involves some aspects to make meaningful words. These are decoding, comprehension, fluency etc. Reading together with learning are foundational skills that significantly influence a learner's academic journey and overall development. At primary level, learners begin to build the essential capability that guide their future educational experiences. However, many learners face challenges in acquiring these skills, leading to reading and learning errors. This research paper, developed on the basis of both primary and secondary data, particularly aims to explore the causes behind these errors among young learners at primary level, focusing on various interrelated factors that contribute to difficulties in reading and learning and providing possible solutions for the same as well.

Key words: Reading, Learning, Young learner, reading disability, Learning disability

Introduction

Reading is the process of expressing own opinion and thinking in a very systematic way; it is a joyful means to attract the audience, here young learners, so that they can be motivated to read something loudly. Reading involves some aspects to make meaningful words. These are decoding, comprehension, fluency etc. Reading together with learning are foundational skills that significantly influence a learner's academic journey and overall development. At primary level, learners begin to build the essential capability that guide their future educational experiences. However, many learners face challenges in acquiring these skills, leading to reading and learning errors. This research paper particularly aims to explore the causes behind these errors among young learners at primary level, focusing on various interrelated factors that contribute to difficulties in reading and learning. By identifying the root causes of these challenges, one can implement targeted interventions and support strategies to enhance literacy outcomes. Ultimately, addressing these

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issues not only encourage a love for reading but also gives an opportunity to the learners with the essential skills they need for lifelong learning.

Learning disability (LD) is a general term that describes specific kinds of learning problems. A learning disability can cause a person to have trouble in learning and using certain skills. The skills most often affected are reading, writing, listening, speaking, reasoning, and doing calculations. Learning disabilities vary from person to person; one person with LD may not have the same kind of learning problems as another person with LD. One person may have trouble with reading and writing. Again, other persons with LD may have problems in understanding math's. Further, other persons may have trouble in each of these areas, as well as with understanding what people are saying. Thus, LD is a group of disorders that affects people's ability to either understand what they see and hear or to link information from different parts of the brain. These limitations can be in many forms, like difficulties in spoken and written language, coordination, self-control, or attention. Such difficulties may delay the learning to reading, writing, or doing calculations by a young learner.

In other words, a learning disability or specific developmental disorder is a disorder that inhibits or interferes with the skills of learning. Learning disabilities are life disabilities; they are seen in children as well as adults. The impairment at times remains undetected throughout the life.

These disabilities create a gap between the true potential and day-to-day productivity and performance. The same learning disabilities that interfere with reading, writing and arithmetic also interfere with cricket, football, getting dressed, keeping the room tidy and with every aspect of life. If a person is not benefited from a regular educational programme and is not socially disadvantaged, mentally limited, or pedagogically deprived and shows no evidence for hard sign of any disorder, then that individual is characterized as learning disability. The young learner who has difficulty in expressing or understanding and cannot read, write or do mathematics within the criterion range as established per school norms is categorized under learning disability. These learners have average or above-average intelligence; their eye sight and hearing capacity are in the normal range; they are not physically handicapped, mentally or emotionally disturbed. But they exhibit difficulties in basic psychological processes responsible for listening, speaking, reading, writing and doing arithmetic. They face greater difficulty in language than in non-language areas. Teachers of such young learners are likely to assume that they (young learners) cannot learn or are mildly mentally disturbed whereas they are not.

The ability to read is not inborn like the ability to speak. A learner does not acquire an ability to read, simply by watching and listening while others read. Reading is a skill that must be intentionally learned. School learning depends largely on reading competence, thus early and sustained failure in reading can have demoralizing consequences in the lives of poor readers and their families and in the socio-economic life of the community as well.

Reading as a fundamental skill serves as the foundation for academic success, particularly in primary education. However, many students encounter various challenges that delay their reading development. Understanding these reading and learning errors is crucial for educators, parents and policymakers as they can significantly impact a learner's educational journey.

Reading is also a critical skill that forms the foundation for a learner's academic journey and overall development. However, many learners of primary school face reading difficulties that can affect their progress in school and beyond. Defining Reading difficulties encompass a range of challenges that prevent learners from reading at expected levels for their age and grade. These difficulties may manifest as struggles with decoding words, poor comprehension or a lack of fluency in reading. They can vary in the society and may be associated with specific learning disabilities, such as dyslexia or arise from environmental factors such as inadequate exposure to language.

Learning errors among young learners is a significant area of concern for educators and parents alike. As children enters into their educational journey, they encounter various challenges that can hamper their understanding and preservation of knowledge. These errors can manifest in numerous ways, including misconceptions in subjects like math and science, difficulties in reading comprehension or challenges in following instructions.

Understanding the nature and causes of these learning errors is crucial for developing effective teaching strategies and interventions. By identifying the underlying factors contributing to these mistakes, one can better support learners in overcoming obstacles, fostering a more conducive learning environment and enhancing their overall academic performance. Addressing learning errors not only aids individual learner development but also promotes a more inclusive and effective educational system.

Objectives

1. To understand various causes behind reading and learning errors among young learners at primary level, focusing on various interrelated factors that contribute to difficulties in reading and learning.
2. To highlight types of error and possible interventions to deal with the problem.
3. To analyse the collected primary data and present the discussion.
4. To provide suggestions to deal with the issues.

Significance

The study is significant as it provides an insight into how students think and learn and help teachers to understand their learning styles; it helps learners to identify and correct their mistakes and recognize patterns in their misunderstandings. It further allows learners to make and correct errors so that they can learn. The paper suggests few remedies also to correct the errors.

Methodology

The research paper is developed based on primary data; secondary sources of information include books, journals and various web sources. The study area is a remote village known as Indranagar Khasia Punjee under Udharbond LAC of Cachar district in Assam. The geographical location of the school (where the study was conducted) as well as the village is a remote area where the public transportation and electronic communication system is a major barrier which often affects the daily life of the people of the village for livelihood. This situation often badly affecting the learning environment among the children of the area. The study was conducted on the learners of Class IV and V of Indranagar Khasia Punjee village who are regularly facing difficulties in reading like decoding, pronunciation and vocabulary. A total number of 50 learners comprises the total number of respondents from both classes; all the respondents were given a questionnaire comprising questions relating financial conditions of the family, geographical barriers, social discrimination, educational background of the family, communication barrier. Observation as a method of data collection has also been used during the reading (*Pothon*).

The research paper aims to understand the learning errors among the young learners of primary school. Data have been studied from as many angles as possible to explore the new facts.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Class

Status	Number of Respondents		Percentage (%)
	Male	Female	
Class - IV	15	10	50
Class - V	13	12	50
Total	28	22	100
Grand Total	50		100

Source: Primary Data Collected by author

Table 1 presents the respondents by classes and gender wise. From the above percentage distribution, it is noticed that a total number of 50 respondents are there; of which 28 numbers are male and 22 females. This includes both the classes.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Mother Tongue

Mother Tongue	No. of Respondents		Percentage (%)
	Male	Female	
Bengali	10	5	30
Khasi	25	10	70
Total	35	15	100
Grand Total	50		100

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 tries to unveil the respondent's opinion about their mother tongue. Glancing through the percentage distribution, one can notice that 30 per cent of the respondents belongs to Bengali community i.e., their Mother Tongue is Bengali. Among them 10 numbers of respondents are male and 5 are females while the rest 70 per cent belongs to Khasi community i.e., their mother tongue is Khasi. Among them 25 numbers of respondents are males and 10 are females.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents by Kinds of Reading Materials

Kinds of Reading Materials	No. of Respondents		Percentage (%)
	Male	Female	
Newspaper	3	1	8
Textbook	20	6	52
Comics	10	4	28
Magazine	4	2	12
Total	37	13	100
Grand Total	50		100

Source: Primary Data

Table 3 shows the interest level of respondents in reading different reading materials. The majority i.e., 52 per cent are interested in reading Textbooks; out of which 20 numbers of respondents are male and 6 are

females. While 28 per cent responded for Comics; of which 10 are males and 4 are females. 12 per cent shows interest in reading magazine. Among them 4 numbers of respondents are male and 2 are female and rest of 8 per cent raised their hands for Newspaper. From them 3 numbers are male and only 1 is female.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents by FLN Materials

FLN Material	No. of Respondents		Percentage (%)
	Male	Female	
Chart	15	5	40
Abacus	10	9	38
Measuring Cup	5	6	22
Grand Total	50		100

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 shows reading by using different FLN Materials by the respondents. The majority i.e., 40 per cent are interested in reading by using of Chart; among them 15 numbers of respondents are male and 5 are females while 38 per cent likes to read by Abacus. Out of which 10 numbers of respondents are male and 9 are females. 22 per cent are interested in using of Measuring Cup for reading, of which 5 numbers are male and 6 are females.

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents for Preferable Language of Reading

Language	No. of Respondents		Percentage (%)
	Male	Female	
Bengali	4	2	12
English	10	3	26
Khasi	25	6	62
Grand Total	50		100

Source: Primary Data

Table 5 shows the preferable language of reading by the respondents. The majority i.e., 62 per cent prefers Khasi language for reading; among them 25 numbers of respondents are male and 6 are females. While 26 percent prefers English language for reading; in which 10 numbers of respondents are male and 3 are female and the rest of 12 per cent prefers Bengali language for reading, out of which 4 numbers of respondents are male and only 2 are females.

Table 6: Distribution of Respondents for Pothon

Pothon	No. of Respondents		Percentage (%)
	Male	Female	
Yes	6	6	24
No	10	4	28
Don't know	15	9	48
Grand Total	50		100

Source: Primary Data

Table 6 shows the comfortability of the respondents regarding *Pothon*. The majority i.e., 48 per cent responds for 'Don't Know'. Among them 15 numbers of respondents are male and 9 are females whereas 28 per cent said 'No to *Pothon*', of which 10 numbers of respondents are male and 4 are females. 24 per cent held 'yes' to *Pothon*, of which 6 numbers of respondents are male and the rest are female.

Interpretations

Interpretation of reading and learning errors among young learners involves identifying the types of mistakes children make during the process of acquiring reading and other academic skills. These errors can be categorized into various types. Below mentioned are some key aspects:

Types of Errors:

Phonological Errors: Difficulties with decoding or sounding out words. learners may confuse with similar-sounding words (e.g., "bat" vs. "hat") or fail to link sounds with letters effectively. This could indicate a need for more phonic awareness practice.

Reading Comprehension Errors: Learners may understand words at a root level but fail to identify the meaning of sentences or paragraphs. This causes from insufficient vocabulary or weak skills.

Word Recognition Issues: Struggling to recognize uncommon words or irregular words that don't follow phonetic rules.

Fluency Problems: Inability to read smoothly or at an appropriate place, often due to lack of practice or foundational reading skills.

Spelling and Writing Errors: Misunderstanding of word structures, leading to repeated misspellings or poor handwriting. This can also affect reading fluency.

Reversal Errors: Confusing letters like "b" and "d," or numbers like "3" and "5," is common among young children but can also be a sign of dyslexia or other learning disabilities if persistent.

Causes of Errors:

Cognitive Factors:

Dyslexia: A common learning disability that affects the ability to decode written words and link them to their sounds. Children with dyslexia may show consistent patterns of reading and spelling errors.

Attention Deficit Disorders (ADD /ADHD): Students may struggle with maintaining attention, leading to incomplete understanding or careless mistakes during reading and learning.

Memory Issues: Working memory difficulties can make it hard for students to remember sequences of letters, words, or instructions, resulting in repeated errors.

Environmental Factors:

Lack of Exposure to Books: Students who haven't been exposed to reading-rich environments or who don't have access to age-appropriate reading materials may struggle to develop basic literacy skills.

Inconsistent Teaching Methods: If the approach of teaching reading and writing is not systematic, children may not receive the support for reading or *Pothon* skills.

Limited Support at Home: Families who do not give priority to reading, or who may lack the resources or time to help, can contribute to a child's slower progress in reading and learning.

Psychosocial Factors:

Low Self-Esteem or Anxiety: Struggling with reading can lead to frustration, lowering confidence and creating a cycle of avoidance or anxiety that further hampers learning.

Lack of Motivation: If the student finds reading or learning tasks too difficult, they might be disappointed, leading to further errors and lack of improvement.

Interventions:

Early Screening and Diagnosis: Identifying reading and learning issues early can help in providing targeted interventions, whether through special education services.

Phonics-based Instruction: Structured phonics programs can help students develop the ability to decode words more effectively.

Reading Comprehension Strategies: Teacher students' strategies for understanding the meaning of texts, like summarizing, questioning, and visualizing, can improve comprehension.

Differentiated Instruction: Personalizing teaching methods to individual needs can address specific errors or difficulties, helping students progress at their own pace.

Increased Practice and Motivation: Regular reading practice, positive reinforcement, and building a supportive, encouraging learning environment can help build confidence and skill.

Role of Educators

Educators should be watchful in identifying reading difficulties, offer individualized support, and use a variety of teaching methods. They should create an environment where students feel safe to make mistakes and learn from them, as well as offer feedback that guides improvement.

Conclusion and Suggestions

Understanding reading and learning errors among young learners involves a comprehensive approach that considers cognitive, emotional, and environmental factors. Early detection, targeted interventions and supportive teaching can help address these errors and set students on a path to becoming confident and competent readers and learners.

Reading and learning errors among young learners are thus common challenges that can significantly impact a child's academic progress and self-esteem. These errors often stem from various factors such as learning disabilities (e.g., dyslexia), attention issues (e.g., ADHD), or lack of early intervention. If not addressed promptly, these challenges can persist, leading to long-term difficulties in academic achievement and personal development. However, with early identification, tailored interventions, and supportive teaching methods, many of these learning difficulties can be mitigated. Implementing inclusive education, where students receive personalized support in a classroom setting, allows for diverse learning needs to be addressed effectively.

Furthermore, fostering a positive, inclusive environment in schools - where every student feels valued and supported - can improve not only academic outcomes but also emotional wellbeing and social integration.

By focusing on individualized support, ongoing assessments, and providing necessary resources, primary school educators can significantly enhance the learning experience for all students, ensuring they are equipped to succeed both in school and beyond.

Thus, recovering from reading and learning errors in primary school students requires a holistic approach that combines early identification, tailored teaching strategies, and consistent support. Following are few suggestions to help learners overcome these challenges:

1. Early Diagnosis and Assessment:

Screen for learning difficulties: Use tools like phonemic awareness tests, reading fluency assessments, and attention evaluations to identify any underlying issues early.

Collaborate with specialists: Work with special education teachers, speech-language pathologists, or educational psychologists to diagnose learning disorders like dyslexia, ADHD, or dyscalculia.

2. Individualized Instruction:

Differentiated teaching: Adapt lessons to meet the varied needs of students. This could include using visual aids, hands-on activities, and breaking down complex tasks into manageable steps.

One-on-one tutoring: Provide additional support through small group instruction or individualized tutoring. Focus on reinforcing weak areas like reading comprehension, letter recognition, and phonic skills.

3. Use of Multisensory Approaches:

Multisensory learning: Engage multiple senses (sight, sound, touch) to reinforce learning. For example, when teaching reading, use tactile activities (like sandpaper letters) or visual aids (such as color-coded word lists).

Interactive tools: Incorporate technology such as speech-to-text software, audiobooks, and educational apps to support reading and writing skills.

4. Reading Programs:

Phonics-based programs: Implement programs that focus on phonics, which teaches the relationship between letters and sounds. This is especially helpful for students with dyslexia or those struggling with word decoding.

Reading fluency practice: Encourage daily reading practice in both the classroom and at home. Use repeated reading techniques (where students read the same text multiple times) to build fluency and confidence.

Sight word practice: Use flashcards and games to help students master high-frequency words that do not follow phonetic rules.

5. Create a Positive Learning Environment:

Build confidence: Celebrate small successes to boost self-esteem and motivate students to keep trying. Avoid negative labelling (e.g., "slow learner") that may harm their confidence.

Reduce distractions: For students with ADHD or attention issues, ensure the classroom environment is conducive to learning, with minimal distractions and structured routines.

Encourage peer support: Pair struggling readers with peers for group reading activities. This can provide encouragement and promote social interaction.

6. Foster Parental Involvement:

Parent-teacher communication: Regularly communicate with parents about their child's progress, challenges, and any home strategies they can use to reinforce learning.

At-home activities: Suggest fun, engaging reading and writing activities that parents can do with their child, such as reading together, playing word games, or keeping a simple journal.

7. Provide Structured Feedback:

Ongoing assessments: Regularly assess students' progress and adjust teaching strategies as needed. Use formative assessments like quizzes, oral readings, or writing assignments.

Immediate feedback: Offer positive reinforcement and corrective feedback immediately after tasks to help students recognize mistakes and learn from them.

8. Focus on Executive Function Skills:

Organizational tools: Teach students how to organize their learning materials, use checklists, and create visual schedules to improve task completion and time management.

Memory aids: Use mnemonic devices, graphic organizers, and visual charts to help students organize and retain information better.

9. Incorporate Physical Activity:

Movement breaks: For students with attention difficulties, short physical activity breaks can help reduce restlessness and improve focus when they return to learning tasks.

Kinesthetic learning: Use physical movement as part of the learning process, such as acting out words or using large gestures to represent concepts.

10. Professional Support and Therapy:

Speech and language therapy: For students with specific language issues, speech therapy can help improve communication and language processing skills.

Occupational Therapy: For children with dysgraphia or fine motor difficulties, occupational therapy can provide strategies to improve handwriting and motor skills.

By combining these strategies, teachers, parents, and specialists can work together to help young learners of primary level recover from reading and learning challenges, ensuring they reach their full potential in their educational journey.

Inclusive Education refers to an approach where all learners, regardless of their physical, intellectual, emotional, or linguistic challenges, are educated together in mainstream schools. This approach values diversity and strives to create an environment where every child can participate fully and equally in the educational process. It promotes the idea that every learner, including those with disabilities or learning difficulties, should have access to the same quality of education in the least restrictive environment possible. Special Attention in the context of inclusive education refers to the targeted support and adaptations should

be provided to learners who need additional assistance to succeed. This support can be tailored to the individual needs of learners with disabilities or learning difficulties, ensuring they are not left behind in a regular classroom setting.

References:

- American Psychiatric Association (Ed.) (2013). Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (DSM-5®) (5th ed.). Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Publishing.
- Bender, W. N. (2004). Learning disabilities: characteristics, identification, and teaching strategies. Boston, MA: Pearson/Allyn and Bacon.
- Darabi, A., Arrington, T. L., & Sayilir, E. (2018). Learning from failure: A meta-analysis of the empirical studies. Educational Technology Research and Development, 66, 1101–1118. 10.1007/s11423-018-9579-9 [DOI] [Google Scholar]
- Deshmukh, V. D., Nasir, Eram. (2021). Bridging the Gap: Reading difficulties and Identifying Reading Difficulties among children with and without special needs in inclusive setup. International Journal for Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Field, 7 (10) 2455-0620. WWW.IJIRMF.COM
- Gautam, A. (2023). Learning Disability among school children: Role of Psychological Intervention. International journal of Indian Psychology, 11(3), 2239-2243. DIP:18.01.211.20231103, DOI: 10.25215/1103.211
- Kapur, M. (2010). Productive failure in mathematical problem solving. Instructional Science, 38, 523–550. 10.1007/s11251-009-9093-x [DOI] [Google Scholar]
- Kapur, M. (2014b). Productive failure in learning math. Cognitive Science, 38(5), 1008–1022. 10.1111/cogs.12107 [DOI] [PubMed] [Google Scholar]
- Umadevi, M. R. (1997). Effectiveness of a remedial programme on improving reading comprehension skills among dyslexic children. Kuvempu university. Sixty surveys of educational research (Vol.I, 19932000). New Delhi: NCERT.
- Ramaa, S. (1990). Two decades of research on learning disabilities in India. Dyslexia. Vol.6(4).

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